

Magnesium Sulphate and Dexmedetomidine as an Adjuvant to 0.5% Ropivacaine in Infraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block : A Comparative Study

REBEKAH EDNA NOBLE ¹, KEERTHANA.P², BALASUBRAMANIAN S.³

- 1) Post Graduate, Department of anesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre
- 2) Assistant Professor, Department of anesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre
- 3) Professor, Department of anesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

Received: July 09, 2025

Accepted: Aug 01, 2025

Published: Aug 02, 2025

Abstract

Background: Comparing the clinical effectiveness of MgSO₄ and dexamethasone as adjuvants to ropivacaine in infraclavicular BPB in patients having upper limb operations was the goal of the current investigation, which remains an unsolved debate.

Methods: This Randomized controlled study was conducted in the department of Anesthesiology among the cases underwent upper limb surgery under Infraclavicular Brachial Plexus block at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Institute during January 2026 to June 2025. A total of ninety cases were included in the study. Under IC-BPB, Group M received magnesium sulphate (150 mg) as adjuvant along with ropivacaine 0.5% and group D received dexmedetomidine (100 µg) when added to ropivacaine 0.5% with 45 cases in each group. Analysis was done using SPSS 19.

Results: In this study group and group D were similar in terms of demographic profile. Group D is remarkably better in terms of onset and duration of sensory and motor block with reduced pain score at 12 hours postoperatively with reduced consumption of rescue analgesia.

Conclusion: For infraclavicular BPB, magnesium sulphate or dexmedetomidine is a helpful adjuvant to ropivacaine in extending the duration of analgesia. Although the frequency of intraoperative hypotension and bradycardia was greater than MS, dexmedetomidine produced faster onset times, longer durations of SB and MB, and longer durations of analgesia with reduced use of postoperative rescue analgesia.

Key words: Infraclavicular block, magnesium sulphate, dexmedetomidine

Introduction

Blocking peripheral nerves lowers the need for analgesics, decreases surgical discomfort and nausea, and increases patient satisfaction¹. Surgical anaesthesia of the upper extremities and shoulder is possible by blocking the brachial plexus at many points, from the roots to the terminal branches². Because of its simplicity, dependability, and high success rate, the infraclavicular BPB is frequently utilized³. The peripheral nerve stimulator, which uses an insulated needle and a low intensity electric current (up to 2.5 mA) for a brief period of time (0.05–1 ms) to produce a defined muscle twitch response, is a very successful method for identifying appropriate needle placement⁴.

An aminoamide local anaesthetic called ropivacaine inhibits peripheral nerves that operate on sodium channels that are voltage-dependent. Compared to bupivacaine, it is less harmful to the heart and central nervous system⁵. Compared to bupivacaine, ropivacaine is more motor sparing and has a similar duration of action⁶. To create a rapid, dense, and long-lasting block, a variety of adjuvants were added to local anaesthetics, including dexamethasone, α 2 adrenergic agonist, opioids, MS, epinephrine, and midazolam⁷. Down with its anti-inflammatory properties, dexamethasone is a very strong and very selective glucocorticoid that works by obstructing the nociceptive impulse that passes down the unmyelinated C fibers^{8,9}.

MgSO₄ is another adjuvant that is frequently utilized. Magnesium's anti-nociceptive actions stem from its ability to control calcium influx into cells and its antagonistic effects on N-methyl D-aspartate receptors, which limit central sensitization from peripheral nociceptive stimulation and are utilized to extend the block's duration¹⁰.

The rationale for this study stems from the need to identify a more effective and longer-lasting analgesic strategy for patients undergoing upper limb surgeries . While ropivacaine is a common and standard choice, its variable duration and slower onset warrant exploration of some adjuvant to enhance its effectiveness . Dexmedetomidine, with its favourable hemodynamic stability and anti-inflammatory effects, presents a viable option . MgSO₄ with its superior anti- nociceptive properties also presents another viable option .

The efficacy of MgSO₄ and dexmedetomidine as adjuvants to bupivacaine and ropivacaine for different peripheral nerve blocks has not been well studied. Nevertheless, none of these trials have compared MgSO₄ and dexmedetomidine as ropivacaine supplements, particularly for infraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block .

By comparing these two agents, this study aims to bridge the knowledge gap and guide clinical decision-making.

This prospective study seeks to compare the clinical effectiveness of MgSO₄ versus dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to local anaesthetic ropivacaine 0.5%, when giving infraclavicular blocks in patients undergoing upper limb surgeries .The findings could contribute to optimizing analgesic regimens, improving patient outcomes, eliminate the need for general anaesthesia and subsequently reduce the unnecessary use of opioids as well as its adverse side effects and supporting evidence-based practice.

Primary Objectives

1. To evaluate and compare the effect of magnesium sulphate and dexmedetomidine when added to ropivacaine 0.5 % for Infraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block on the duration of analgesia.
2. To assess and compare postoperative pain intensity using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) between the two groups at predefined time intervals (1 hr, 2 hr, 4 hr, 6 hr, 8 hr, 12hr ,18 hr and 24 hr).

Secondary Objectives

1. To evaluate the onset of motor and sensory blocks between the two groups
2. To compare the duration of sensory and motor block between the two groups
3. To record and analyse adverse effects (sedation, bradycardia, hypotension, or local anaesthetic toxicity) associated with either intervention.
4. To assess the total dose of rescue analgesia consumed within the first 24 hours postoperatively.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This was a prospective, randomized, double-blind, comparative study conducted at SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre among the cases underwent upper limb surgery under Infraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Institute during January 2026 to June 2025. The study adhered to the CONSORT guidelines for randomized controlled trials.

Study Population

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 20–60 years classified as ASA I or II scheduled for upper limb surgeries

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with comorbidities (cardiac, respiratory, renal, or hepatic disease).
- Allergy to local anaesthetics or dexmedetomidine or magnesium sulphate.
- Pregnant or lactating women.

Sample Size and Randomization: A total of 90 patients were enrolled and randomly allocated into two groups (n=45 each) using a computer-generated randomization table:

- **Group M:** Received **magnesium (150 mg) as adjuvant along with ropivacaine 0.5%.**
- **Group D:** Received **dexmedetomidine (100 mg) as adjuvant along with ropivacaine 0.5%..**

Allocation concealment was maintained using sequentially numbered, opaque, sealed envelopes.

Blinding: The surgeon, anaesthesiologist, and patients were blinded to group allocation. The study drug was prepared by an independent anaesthesiologist who had no role in the research.

Anesthetic and Surgical Protocol

Preoperative Preparation:

- A pre-anaesthetic checkup was performed, and patients were educated on the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain assessment (0–10)..

Intraoperative Management:

- On arrival to the operating room, patients were monitored with standards monitoring including electrocardiography, pulse oximetry, and non invasive blood pressure.

Intervention:

After skin preparation, 3 ml of lidocaine 1% was injected subcutaneously at the site of injection. Infraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block was performed with the guidance of ultrasound while the patient in supine position and his head slightly turned to the other side with the upper extremity abducted 90°. The entry site is identified at 2 cm medially and 2 cm caudal to the coracoid process. The probe of ultrasound was placed medial to the coracoids process in the parasagittal plane to identify the axillary artery and the three cords of the brachial plexus. The Local Anaesthetic 7 ml solution was then be injected around each cord.

Injection of Local Anaesthetic solution was given slowly with frequent aspiration every 3 ml to avoid unintentional intravascular injection. The Sensory Block and Motor Block was assessed every 3 min in the first 30 min after injection of Local Anaesthetic and every 30 min postoperatively till the infraclavicular block is worn off. The Sensory Block was graded: 0 = normal sensation; 1 = loss of sensation to pinprick; and 2 = loss of touch sensation.

SCORE	LEVEL OF SENSATION
0	NORMAL SENSATION
1	LOSS OF SENSATION TO PINPRICK
2	LOSS OF SENSATION TO TOUCH

The onset time of the Sensory Block is the time interval from injection of Local Anaesthetic till the complete Sensory Block achieved. The duration of the Sensory Block is the time interval between the onset of the complete Sensory Block and complete resolution of the Sensory Block. Duration of analgesia is the time interval between the onset of the complete Sensory Block and the first dose of postoperative analgesia. The Motor Block was graded according to modified Bromage scale. The onset time of the Motor Block is the time interval between injection of Local Anaesthetic and time of the complete Motor Block. The duration of Motor Block is the time interval between the onset of the complete Motor Block and complete resolution of the Motor Block. The block was considered successful when the Sensory Block is 2 and Motor Block s 0 within 30 min after injection of the local analgesia. Otherwise, the block will be considered as failed or inadequate block and the patients would receive general anaesthesia or analgesia to complete the surgical intervention. These patients will be excluded from the study.

Intraoperative MAP and heart rate (HR) were recorded preoperatively and every 15 min after the administration of LA solution till the end of surgery.

Postoperative Assessment

- Pain was assessed using a 10-cm visual analogue scale (VAS) and recorded at admission to postoperative care unit and 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 18, and 24 h postoperatively.
- Patients received postoperative analgesia when VAS is >3.

- Time to first rescue analgesia, total analgesic consumption, and adverse effects (nausea, vomiting, sedation, bradycardia, hypotension) were documented.

Statistical Analysis: Analysis was done using SPSS 19. Chi square test and Independent sample t test were used. P value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Ethical Considerations: Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained. All participants gave written informed consent. Confidentiality and patient safety were maintained throughout the study.

Results

In this study among group M participants 12.2% of them were ≤ 30 years, 20% of the participants were in 31-45 years and 17.8% of the participants were in 46-60 years of age while 13.3% of the participants were in ≤ 30 years, 16.7% of the participants were in 31-45 years and 20% of the participants were in 46-60 years of age. There was no significant association recorded between group M and group D cases (p value =0.7531). There was no significant association recorded for gender between the groups in this study. BMI was found to be normal among 26.7% of the cases, 16.7% of the participants were overweight and 6.7% of the participants were obese among group M cases whereas BMI was normal among 26.7% of the cases, overweight among 15.6% of the cases and 7.8% of the participants were obese with no statistical association between the groups for BMI (p value =0.894). On assessing the ASA status between group M and group D participants it was found that there was no significant association for ASA (p value =0.715). Similarly the association for side of block and surgical site was also not significant between the groups.

Table 1: Clinical Profile of the study participants

Variables	Group M	Group D	p value
Age group			
≤ 30 years	11 (12.2)	12 (13.3)	0.7531
31-45 years	18 (20)	15 (16.7)	
46-60 years	16 (17.8)	18 (20)	
Gender			
Male	25 (27.8)	23 (25.6)	0.836
Female	15 (16.7)	17 (18.9)	
BMI			
Normal	24 (26.7)	24 (26.7)	0.894
Overweight	15 (16.7)	14 (15.6)	
Obese	6 (6.7)	7 (7.8)	
ASA status			
Class I	10 (11.1)	13 (14.4)	0.715
Class II	35 (38.9)	32 (35.6)	
Side of block			
Left	21 (23.3)	23 (25.6)	0.837
Right	19 (21.1)	17 (18.9)	
Operation site			
Elbow	10 (11.1)	09 (10)	0.764
Forearm	19 (21.1)	17 (18.9)	
Wrist & Hand	16 (17.8)	19 (21.1)	

The difference in mean onset of sensory block, onset of motor block, duration of sensory block and duration of motor block was noted to be statistically significant with p values of 0.000, 0.0104, 0.0233 and 0.000 respectively.

Table 2: Comparison of sensory block and motor block duration between the groups

Parameter	Group M	Group D	p value
Onset of sensory block (in mis)	15.1±1.2	13.3±2.4	0.000*
Onset of motor block (in mis)	16.6±2.5	15.3±2.2	0.0104*
Duration of sensory block (in mins)	189.6±52.4	212.5±42.2	0.0233*
Duration of motor block (in mins)	149.4±33.5	192.6±37.8	0.000*

*Significant

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

In this current study the mean difference in VAS at post-operative period 2 hours was statistically insignificant between the groups while the difference in means at post-operative period 12 hours between both the groups was significant with p value of 0.0015. The mean VAS at post-operative period 24 hours was found to be insignificant with p value 0.9026. The mean difference in time taken for rescue analgesia was also noted to be highly significant between the groups with p value of 0.000.

Table 3: Mean VAS score at different time duration and rescue analgesia

Parameter	Group M	Group D	p value
VAS at postop 2 hrs	2.1±1.6	1.8±0.9	0.2761
VAS at postop 12 hrs	5.6±1.9	4.7±2.7	0.0015*
VAS at post op 24 hrs	4.2±2.4	4.5±2.1	0.9026
Mean time taken for first rescue analgesia	6.4±2.1	8.6±2.5	0.000*

*Significant

Figure 3:

Discussion

Findings of the present study were comparable with the study in which the effectiveness of MS and dexamethasone with ropivacaine as an adjuvant in SCB was compared by Balaji D et al¹¹. The time it took for sensory blocking to start varied significantly between the two groups, they reported. The average onset time for Group RM, which was given with 300 mg of magnesium sulfate and 30 cc of 0.5% ropivacaine, was 13.27 minutes. However, Group RD, which received 8 mg of dexamethasone and 30 ml of 0.5% ropivacaine, suffered sensory blocking considerably faster, with an average duration of 4.35 minutes. Additionally, the time it took for the different groups to develop motor

obstruction varied significantly. The motor blockade onset time for Group RM was 15.20 minutes, while the motor blockade onset time for Group RD was much faster, with a mean of 5.92 minutes. Compared to Group RM, Group RD experienced sensory suppression for a much longer duration. Group RD experienced a much longer duration of sensory blockade, averaging 1020.4 minutes, whereas Group RM experienced an average sensory block duration of 436.21 minutes. The RD group's post-operative VAS scores after 24 hours were significantly lower. In comparison to the RD group, the RM group used more diclofenac sodium injections overall. The block was successfully finished by both groups with no intraoperative or postoperative issues. They said that the administration of dexamethasone in SC-BPB decreases the total quantity of analgesics needed, increases the duration of both sensory and motor block, and delays the time until the first analgesic usage. By combining magnesium sulfate and dexmedetomidine (DEX) with bupivacaine, AbdAlsalam MA et al¹² sought to examine the effects of USG lumbar plexus block on postoperative analgesia and the surgical procedure that followed. For 12 and 18 hours in BM and BD, respectively, they discovered that the research groups' pain levels had dramatically dropped. Additionally, the BD group saw a substantial drop at 2, 4, 6, 8, and 12 hours after surgery, which was smaller than that of the BM group. Compared to the BM group, the BD group's delay to the initial analgesic appeal was noticeably longer. In contrast to posterior lumbar plexus block using 22 ml of bupivacaine 0.5% with magnesium sulfate 150 mg, they asserted that posterior lumbar-plexus block using 22 ml of bupivacaine 0.5% with DEX 1 µg/kg reduces pain score, opioid consumption, prolongs duration of analgesia, improves hemodynamic stability, and produces the best postoperative outcome for patient satisfaction. With fewer doses of postoperative rescue analgesia, DEX offers a quicker onset time, longer durations of MB, and prolonged intervals of analgesia.

When doing USG interscalene blocks for arthroscopic shoulder surgery in an ambulatory situation, Margulis R et al¹³ examined the analgesic duration of the use of dexmedetomidine and dexamethasone as adjuvants to 0.5% ropivacaine. They discovered that when comparing dexmedetomidine, dexamethasone, and no adjuvant, there was no statistically significant difference in the amount of opioids used 24 and 48 hours after surgery. On the other hand, dexmedetomidine dramatically reduced intraoperative opioid usage when compared to dexamethasone plus ordinary 0.5% ropivacaine. When using dexamethasone may not be appropriate, dexmedetomidine is an acceptable substitute as an adjuvant for peripheral nerve blockade due to its safe side effect profile. The therapeutic effectiveness of dexamethasone and MS as adjuvants to ropivacaine in patients experiencing SC-BPB for upper limb surgery was compared by Tewari S et al¹⁴. They found that Group RD experienced sensory and motor block much more quickly than Group RM. Additionally, Group RD's sensory and motor block duration was much longer than Group RM's. Group RD had analgesia for a longer period of time than group RM. Group RM had a substantially greater percentage of those taking two or more rescue analgesic doses than Group RD. They said that during SC-BPB, Dexamethasone performed better than MgSO₄ as an adjuvant to ropivacaine. Elyazed MM et al¹⁵ examined how the quality of infraclavicular BPB was affected by the addition of dexmedetomidine and MS to ropivacaine. In comparison to the control group, they observed that dexmedetomidine and MS produced longer durations of analgesia and lower use of postoperative rescue analgesia; dexmedetomidine produced the greatest length of analgesia. Compared to the control and MS groups, dexmedetomidine produced the quickest onset timings and the longest periods of both SB and MB. The incidence of bradycardia and hypotension was greater in the dexmedetomidine group. In order to extend the duration of analgesia for infraclavicular BPB, they came to the conclusion that MS or dexmedetomidine is a helpful adjuvant to ropivacaine. Though it demonstrated a higher rate of intraop hypotension and bradycardia than MS, dexmedetomidine offered both SB and MB a faster start and longer duration, as well as a longer duration of analgesia with less use of postoperative rescue analgesia.

Using bupivacaine, Kumar S et al¹⁶ examined the effects of perineural dexmedetomidine and MS on the start and course of SC-BPB. They observed that compared to Grade M, the start of sensory and motor block occurred much more quickly in Grade D. In Grade D, the sensory and motor block lasted noticeably longer than in Grade M. During the intraoperative phase, the groups' mean arterial pressures were similar. However, the dexmedetomidine group's mean heart rate was noticeably lower. There were no further negative events noted. They said that when administered for BPB, intravenous dexmedetomidine plus 25 ml of bupivacaine (0.5%) accelerated the onset of sensory and motor block and extended its duration without causing any negative side effects. The effectiveness of MgSO₄ and dexmedetomidine as adjuvants to ropivacaine in SC-BPB was compared by Shukla U et al¹⁷. In comparison to patients receiving MgSO₄, they found that Dexmedetomidine results in an earlier start of sensory and motor block, a longer length of sensory and motor block, a longer duration of analgesia, and less postoperative rescue analgesia. Dexmedetomidine was associated with a greater incidence of bradycardia, hypotension, and sedation. The purpose of Elmaleh AB et al¹⁸ was to compare how MS and Dexmedetomidine added to lidocaine affected the length and onset of SC-BPB in patients having upper limb surgery. They found that group D's motor and sensory block duration was statistically significantly longer than group M's. Group M's motor block lasted 277.2 minutes, while Group D's was 482.5 minutes. Group M's time to first analgesia was 5.1 hours, whereas group D's was 8.7 hours. When comparing group M to group D, a statistically significant increase in the overall amount of analgesia eaten was found. They said that the duration of sensory and motor block in SC-BPB is extended when MS or dexmedetomidine is added to lidocaine. Improved postop analgesia with reduced analgesic needs was seen by both the MS and Dexmedetomidine groups.

The effects of adding MS (MS) and low dosage dexamethasone (LLD) to ropivacaine in SCBPB during elective upper limb procedures were compared by Jalili S et al¹⁹. They observed that the MS group had motor and sensory block more quickly than the LDD and NS groups. In contrast to the MS and NS groups, the LDD group experienced a lengthier sensory blackout. Compared to the NS group, the LDD group had motor block and analgesia for a much longer period of time. This change did not, however, significantly affect the MS group. When it came to overall opioid consumption and VAS at the moment of sensory restoration, there was no difference between the LDD and MS groups. Nonetheless, there were notable differences between the two groups and the NS group. In contrast to MS, they asserted that LDD extended the duration of the motor and sensory block and analgesia. Using either bupivacaine, bupivacaine-MS, or bupivacaine-dexmedetomidine, Mohamad A et al²⁰ assessed the post-operative analgesic effects of USG interscalene BPB in planned shoulder operations performed under GA. There was a substantial reduction in HR, MAP, VAS, onset of sensory block and first analgesic requirements, total dose of rescue analgesic, and prolongation in sensory block in the Mg group & Dex group compared to the control group, and the Dex group was superior to the Mg group. However, they reported no significant differences in age, sex, ASA, duration & type of surgery, or sedation score. When added to bupivacaine 0.25% in USG interscalene BPB, they found that Dexmedetomidine 100µg was superior to MgSO₄ 200mg. This was demonstrated by the prolongation of sensory block, the improvement of post-op analgesia, the reduction in the need for rescue analgesics, and the provision of desired sedation without adverse effects. Wu J et al²¹ sought to see if combining various local anesthetic adjuncts may extend the SC-BPB's analgesic duration during arthroscopic shoulder surgery. According to their claims, the analgesic efficacy of SC-BPB in combination with dexamethasone, MS, and dexmedetomidine is noticeably better than that of MS and dexmedetomidine alone, as well as much better than that of MS alone. The effects of administering either MS or dexmedetomidine to local anesthetics in USG-SBPB were compared by Hassan MA et al²². They observed that both groups' surgical features and demographic information were similar. Group D experienced sensory and motor block durations that were statistically substantially longer than those of group M, whereas group D's onset timings were statistically significantly shorter than those of group M. Group D's analgesia duration differed from group M's by a statistically significant amount. They came to the conclusion that in US-guided BPB,

dexmedetomidine works better than MS as an adjuvant to LAs. Dexmedetomidine increases the length of sensory and motor block and speeds up its onset. Additionally, dexmedetomidine produces analgesia for a longer period of time than MS.

Conclusion

For infraclavicular BPB, magnesium sulphate or dexmedetomidine is a helpful adjuvant to ropivacaine in extending the duration of analgesia. Although the frequency of intraop hypotension and bradycardia was greater than MS, dexmedetomidine produced faster onset times, longer durations of SB and MB, and longer durations of analgesia with reduced use of postoperative rescue analgesia.

References

1. Jogie J, Jogie JA. A comprehensive review on the efficacy of nerve blocks in reducing postoperative anesthetic and analgesic requirements. *Cureus* 2023;15:e38552.
2. Terese TH, Sandra LK, Denise JW. Peripheral nerve blocks. In: Miller RD, editor. *Miller's Anaesthesia*. 8th ed., Vol. 1. Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunders; 2015. p. 721-51.
3. Taneja P, Singh M, Singh B, Attri JP. Comparison of 0.5% Ropivacaine with 0.5% Ropivacaine and magnesium sulphate in supraclavicular brachial plexus block for forelimb and hand surgeries. *Int J Med Res Rev* 2018;6:136-42.
4. Sethi N, Arora KK, Vaskle P, Bhandari G. A comparative study of peripheral nerve stimulator guided versus ultrasound-guided supraclavicular brachial plexus block for upper limb surgery. *Eur J Cardiovasc Med* 2023;13:499-505.
5. Vainionpää VA, Haavisto ET, Huha TM, Korpi KJ, Nuutinen LS, Hollmén AI, *et al*. A clinical and pharmacokinetic comparison of ropivacaine and bupivacaine in axillary plexus block. *Anesth Analg* 1995;81:534-8.
6. Lawrence LB. Local anaesthetics. In: Goodman and Gilman's *The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics*. 12th ed. McGraw Hill: New York; 2011. p. 572-608.
7. Sunil R, Amminikkutty CM, Jose S. Dexamethasone as an adjuvant with ropivacaine for supraclavicular brachial plexus block. *J Med Sci Clin Res* 2018;6:1201-7.
8. Rhen T, Cidlowski JA. Antiinflammatory action of glucocorticoids – New mechanisms for old drugs. *N Engl J Med* 2005;353:1711-23.
9. Yousef Metias MF, Sayed-Ahmed A, Hassan A. Effect of adding dexamethasone or magnesium sulphate as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in ultrasound-guided supraclavicular brachial plexus block for upper limb surgeries; a comparative study. *Zagazig Univ Med J* 2021;27:1038-46.
10. Agrawal A, Agrawal S, Payal YS. Effect of continuous magnesium sulfate infusion on spinal block characteristics: A prospective study. *Saudi J Anaesth* 2014;8:78-82.
11. Balaji D, Krishnan CD, Shankar RA, Ganesh SC. To compare the efficacy of magnesium sulphate and dexamethasone with ropivacaine as an adjuvant in supra clavicular block. *Int J Acad Med Pharm*. 2024;6(3):1086-90.
12. AbdAlsalam MA, Mohamed NA. A comparative study between magnesium sulfate and dexmedetomidine as adjuvants to bupivacaine using ultrasound-guided lumbar-plexus block in lower abdominal surgeries. *Al-Azhar Assiut Medical Journal*. 2022 Jan 1;20(1):72-84.
13. Margulis R, Francis J, Tischenkel B, Bromberg A, Pedulla D, Grtisenko K, Cornett EM, Kaye AD, Imani F, Imani F, Shaparin N. Comparison of dexmedetomidine and dexamethasone as adjuvants to ultra-sound guided interscalene block in arthroscopic shoulder surgery: a double-blinded randomized placebo-controlled study. *Anesthesiology and Pain Medicine*. 2021 Jul 4;11(3):e117020.

14. Tewari S, Maurya RG, Rai SK, Maurya I, Sonker SK, Srivastava D. Comparison of Analgesia Efficacy between Magnesium Sulfate and Dexamethasone as an Adjuvant to Ropivacaine in Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block in Patients Undergoing Upper Limb Surgery: A Prospective Randomized Study. *Indian Journal of Pain*. 2025 Jan 1;39(1):11-7.
15. Elyazed MM, Mogahed MM. Comparison of magnesium sulfate and dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to 0.5% ropivacaine in infraclavicular brachial plexus block. *Anesthesia essays and researches*. 2018 Jan 1;12(1):109-15.
16. Kumar S, Shadab M, Prasad S, Kumar G, Kumari S, Prasad C. Comparison of magnesium sulfate and dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to 0.5% ropivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus block. *IOSR J Dent Med Sci*. 2020;19(2):55-64.
17. Shukla U, Singh D, Yadav JB, Azad MS. Dexmedetomidine and magnesium sulfate as adjuvant to 0.5% ropivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus block: a comparative evaluation. *Anesthesia Essays and Researches*. 2020 Oct 1;14(4):572-7.
18. Elmaleh AB, Nassar AM, Mohammed ZA. Comparative Study between Magnesium Sulfate and Dexmedetomidine Added to Lidocaine in Ultrasound Guided Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block in Upper Limb Surgery. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2022 Oct 1;89(1):4715-20.
19. Jalili S, Kavandi D, Gheiasi SF. Comparison of the Effect of Adding Magnesium Sulfate and Low-Dose Dexamethasone to Ropivacaine for Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus (Trunks) Nerve Block in Elective Upper Limb Surgeries: A Prospective Triple-Blind Randomized Clinical Trial. *Journal of Advances in Medical and Biomedical Research*. 2024 Jan 10;32(150):67-78.
20. Mohamad A, Elzeftawy DA, Fayad MB, Ahmed SE. Analgesic Effect of Dexmedetomidine or Magnesium Sulphate Added to Bupivacaine in Interscalene Brachial Plexus Block During Shoulder Arthroscopy. *The Medical Journal of Cairo University*. 2019 Sep 1;87(September):3755-63.
21. Wu J, Chen G, Quan X, Shu H, Duan G, Shu B, Wang T, Huang H, Chen Y, Nie M. Combination of different local anesthetic adjunct for supraclavicular brachial plexus block after arthroscopic shoulder surgery: a prospective randomized controlled trial. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*. 2024 Oct 24;25(1):844.
22. Hassan MA, Abaza K, Fawzy E, Kamel AA. Magnesium Sulphate versus Dexmedetomidine as an Additive to Lidocaine and Bupivacaine in Ultrasound Guided Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block in Upper Limb Surgeries. *Zagazig University Medical Journal*. 2020 Nov 1;26(6):1066-77.